

Physicochemical properties of anionic-nonionic surfactant mixture : α -sulfonatomyristic acid methyl ester (MES) – nonaoxyethylene monododecyl ether ($C_{12}E_9$)[†]

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We report the interfacial, thermodynamic and performance properties of the binary mixture of α -sulfonatomyristic acid methyl ester (MES) and nonaoxyethylene monododecyl ether ($C_{12}E_9$). The critical micelle concentration (cmc), thermodynamics of micellization and adsorption, and minimum area occupied by the surfactant at the air/water interface, micellar aggregation number (Nagg.) have been determined. The mixed micellar composition and interaction parameter (β^m) are also evaluated. The estimated interaction parameter indicates an overall attractive interaction in the mixed micelles. Moreover, the performance properties of pure and mixed surfactant systems like foaming and viscosity are also studied.

Surfactants find extensive applications in various fields due to their property of adsorbing on to surfaces or interfaces and thereby altering to a marked degree, the surface free energy of those surfaces or interfaces¹. In fundamental and applied fields, mixed surfactants are prevalent. The functions and properties of surfactant systems depend on their structural type, concentration and compositions in addition to other factors, viz. temperature, pressure, pH, solvent and additives². Mixed surfactant systems exhibit superior performance properties compared to individual surfactants. Some combinations exhibit synergistic properties, showing a remarkable decrease in surface tension and lower critical micelle concentration (cmc) values than each of the individual surfactant. Thus fundamental studies are essential for exact and detailed understanding of self-organizing behavior of surfactant(s)³. In recent years, studies on different types of combinations formed by different surfactants, such as anionic-cationic⁴, nonionic-nonionic⁵, anionic-nonionic^{6, 7}, nonionic-cationic⁸, anionic-zwitterionic⁹ etc. have been studied. Rationale for selection of nonionic surfactant of the alkyl polyoxyethylene ether, C_nE_m type is its wide use as detergent, solubilizer and emulsifier¹⁰ and α -sulfonato fatty acid methyl esters have superior detergency, high tolerance against calcium ions and good biodegradability^{11,12}.

The present article deals with interaction of nonaoxyethylene monododecyl ether ($C_{12}E_9$) with α -sulfonatomyristic acid methyl ester (MES) in aqueous solution, with refer-

ence to mixed micelle formation, thermodynamics of micellization and adsorption of surfactant at the air/water interface. The micellar aggregation number and the microenvironment of the mixed micelle are also discussed. The intermicellar interactions and the composition of the mixed micelle are also studied using Rubingh's theory¹³. Viscosity and foamability of surfactant solutions are also presented.

Results and discussion

Critical micelle concentration :

The cmc values for aqueous solution of single and binary surfactant systems of different mole fractions at 30, 35, 40 and 45° are presented in Table 1. The cmc values of MES obtained by conductance measurements are in good agreement with those reported in literature¹¹, though the cmc values obtained by surface tension and conductance measurement are different. Variations in cmc values depending on the method of determination have been reported in literature^{14,15}. The cmc values of MES increase with increase in temperature (30–45°), which may be due to the corresponding increase in ionic repulsive forces¹⁶. For the nonionic surfactant – $C_{12}E_9$, the cmc values decrease with increase in temperature, which has generally been observed earlier also^{17,18}. The cmc values of $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant system were evaluated by surface tension measurement only as specific conductance-concentration plot did not show any break. Thus we treated $C_{12}E_9$ /MES surfactant

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Table 1. Critical micelle concentration (cmc) values of C₁₂E₉/MES mixed surfactant system in aqueous media at different temperatures

N _{MES}	cmc (mM)			
	303	308	313	318 K
0.0	0.0812	0.0794	0.0758	0.0741
0.1	0.093	0.088	0.085	0.082
0.3	0.109	0.104	0.099	0.097
0.5	0.120	0.115	0.109	0.107
0.7	0.180	0.109	0.165	0.147
0.9	0.397	0.380	0.346	0.315
1.0	2.39	2.51	2.63	3.16
	3.16 ^a	3.24	3.32	3.48
	(0.634) ^b	(0.641)	(0.646)	(0.656)

^aConductivity data. ^bValues in parenthesis are the degree of ionization of micelle of MES.

mixture as a nonionic one, i.e. mixed micelles are nonionic in nature.

Thermodynamics of micellization and adsorption :

The standard free energy of micellization for a nonionic surfactant is given by the relation¹⁷,

$$\Delta G_m^0 = RT \ln X_{cmc}$$

where X_{cmc} is the cmc in mole fraction scale.

whereas for an ionic surfactant,

$$\Delta G_m^0 = (2 - \alpha) RT \ln X_{cmc}$$

where α is the degree of ionization of micelle. α was computed from the ratio between slopes of the post-micellar and pre-micellar regions of the specific conductance – concentration profile of MES¹⁹. The ΔG_m^0 values are presented in Table 2. The ΔG_m^0 values are all negative and become more negative with increase in temperature, suggesting that formation of micelles becomes relatively more spontaneous. The standard enthalpy ΔH_m^0 and standard entropy ΔS_m^0 of micellization were evaluated from $\Delta G_m^0 - T$

Table 2. The thermodynamic parameters of micellization of C₁₂E₉/MES mixed surfactant system.

N _{MES}	- ΔG_m^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹) at				ΔH_m^0 kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS_m^0 J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	303	308	313	318 K		
0.0	33.8	34.5	35.1	35.8	6.2	132
0.1	33.5	34.2	34.8	35.5	6.5	132
0.3	33.1	33.8	34.4	35	5.0	126
0.5	32.9	33.5	34.2	34.8	5.9	128
0.7	31.8	32.5	33.1	33.9	10.0	138
0.9	29.8	30.5	31.2	31.9	12.6	140
1.0	33.6	33.9	34.3	34.4	-16.7	56

plot. The slope and intercept gave ΔS_m^0 and ΔH_m^0 , respectively. The overall micellization process is endothermic except for MES, where it is exothermic. The ΔS_m^0 values are positive indicating that micellization is entropy-dominated²⁰. The maximum surface excess (Γ_{max}) and minimum area per molecule (A_{min}) of the surfactant at the air/water interface were evaluated using Gibb's adsorption equation²¹ and are presented in Table 3. The lower values of A_{min} in the mixed systems may be due to closer packing at the air-water inter-

Table 3. Maximum surface excess (Γ_{max}) and limiting surface area per molecule (A_{min}) of C₁₂E₉/MES mixed surfactant system

N _{MES}	$\Gamma_{max} \times 10^{10}$ mol cm ⁻² at				A_{min} (nm ²)			
	303	308	313	318 K	303	308	313	318 K
0.0	3.35	3.21	2.45	3.36	0.49	0.52	0.67	0.50
0.1	2.46	1.8	2.10	2.41	0.67	0.75	0.79	0.69
0.3	2.01	2.0	2.05	1.64	0.67	0.76	0.80	0.97
0.5	2.47	2.82	2.10	1.64	0.61	0.52	0.77	1.01
0.7	1.62	2.0	1.67	1.47	1.02	0.83	0.99	1.12
0.9	2.27	2.11	2.27	2.24	0.73	0.78	0.73	0.74
1.0	1.25	1.16	1.08	1.06	1.33	1.43	1.53	1.57

face owing to the decreased repulsion between the oriented headgroups of surfactants. The thermodynamic parameters of adsorption of surfactants at the air/water interface were evaluated using the relation²²,

$$\Delta G_{ad}^0 = \Delta G_m^0 - N \Pi_{cmc} A_{cmc}$$

where N, Π_{cmc} and A_{cmc} are Avogadro number, surface pressure at cmc ($\gamma_0 - \gamma_{cmc}$) and area per molecule at cmc, respectively. The standard state for the adsorbed surfactant here is a hypothetical monolayer at its minimum surface area per molecule but at zero surface pressure. The standard enthalpy, ΔH_{ad}^0 and standard entropy, ΔS_{ad}^0 values were evaluated from $\Delta G_{ad}^0 - T$ plot. The ΔG_{ad}^0 values are negative throughout, indicating that adsorption at the air/water interface takes place spontaneously in pure as well as mixed

Table 4. The thermodynamic parameters of adsorption of C₁₂E₉/MES mixed surfactant system

N _{MES}	- ΔG_{ad}^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹) at				ΔH_{ad}^0 kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS_{ad}^0 J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	303	308	313	318 K		
0.0	40.6	41.6	44.1	43.4	25.2	218
0.1	42.9	45.2	46.9	45.6	15.7	196
0.3	43.0	43.6	44.1	45.7	9.3	172
0.5	39.0	40.0	41.6	43.2	47.2	284
0.7	44.6	41.7	44.8	46.3	6.6	164
0.9	39.3	40.4	40.7	41.5	2.4	138
1.0	48.4	50.3	52.3	53.3	52.6	334

Fig. 1. Enthalpy-entropy compensation plot.

surfactants (Table 4). The ΔH_{ad}^0 values suggest that adsorption process is endothermic and entropy of adsorption values are high, reflecting that there is more freedom for motion of hydrocarbon chains at the interface.

A linear correlation between ΔS_m^0 and ΔH_m^0 as well as ΔS_{ad}^0 and ΔH_{ad}^0 (Fig. 1) was observed for this system which was suggested by Lumry and Rajender²³. The compensation temperature for micellization and adsorption processes are 314 and 281 K, respectively. Such behavior was observed earlier also²⁴ and it implies that at 314 K, the micellization process is independent of structural changes in the system and is dependent only on enthalpic factors²⁵. The β^m values, a measure of interaction between the surfactant molecules in the mixed micelle, are presented in Table 5. β^m values are all negative at all mole fractions of $C_{12}E_9$ /MES system

Table 5. Interaction parameter (β^m) values of $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant system in aqueous media at different temperatures*

N_{MES}	$(\beta^m)^a$			
	303	308	313	318 K
0.1	-	-	-	-
0.3	-1.87/-1.57 ^b (0.0551)	-2.33/-2.06 (0.072)	-2.30/-2.20 (0.067)	-2.50/-2.39 (0.072)
0.5	-3.32/-2.98 (0.178)	-3.57/-3.20 (0.186)	-3.65/-3.36 (0.185)	-3.70/-3.58 (0.182)
0.7	-2.91/-2.55 (0.227)	-3.51/-2.86 (0.236)	-3.64/-3.05 (0.185)	-3.77/-3.64 (0.189)
0.9	-2.55/-2.12 (0.341)	-2.72/-2.32 (0.343)	-3.03/-2.67 (0.344)	-3.46/-3.30 (0.350)

* Values in parenthesis are X_1 , i.e. mole fraction of MES.

^a(-) Iteration did not coalesce.

^bThe data after ' / ' was calculated using cmc of MES by ST measurement.

except $N_{MES} = 0.1$, where the iteration did not coalesce. The negative β^m values suggest an attractive interaction

between the MES and $C_{12}E_9$ headgroups in the mixed micelle leading to electrostatic stabilization. It is evident from Table 1, that the cmc of MES seems to differ when surface tension or conductance methods are used. It is clear that calculated β^m values do differ (maximum ~15%) but the interaction is always attractive in nature.

The activity coefficient values were also evaluated using the relations¹,

$$\ln f_1 = \beta^m (1 - X_1)^2$$

and

$$\ln f_2 = \beta^m (X_1)^2$$

where X_1 is mole fraction of surfactant 1 in the micelle and f_1 and f_2 are the activity coefficients of surfactants 1 and 2, respectively, in the mixed micelle. The f_1 and f_2 values are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Activity coefficient (f_1, f_2) values of $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant system in aqueous media at different temperatures*

N_{MES}	f_1 of anionic surfactant			
	303	308	313	318 K
0.1	-	-	-	-
0.3	0.188 (0.994)	0.134 (0.987)	0.135 (0.989)	0.116 (0.987)
0.5	0.106 (0.900)	0.094 (0.883)	0.089 (0.882)	0.084 (0.884)
0.7	0.175 (0.86)	0.154 (0.836)	0.133 (0.816)	0.118 (0.793)
0.9	0.330 (0.743)	0.309 (0.726)	0.271 (0.698)	0.232 (0.654)

* Values in parentheses are activity coefficient (f_2) of nonionic surfactant.

The f_1 values of MES are lower, suggesting that MES in the mixed micelle is away from the standard state. The f_2 values of $C_{12}E_9$ are higher which increase with increase in

Fig. 2. Micellar aggregation number (N_{agg}) for $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant system.

temperature, indicating that $C_{12}E_9$ in the mixed micelle is near its standard state^{3, 5} (Table 6).

Micellar aggregation number and microenvironment :

Micellar aggregation number (N_{agg}) determined by steady state fluorescence measurements at different mole ratios of binary $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixture are presented in Fig. 2. The aggregation number values of mixtures are larger than that of MES but more or less comparable with $C_{12}E_9$. Such behavior may be due to the presence of $C_{12}E_9$ in the mixed micelle, resulting in screening of interionic interactions in comparison with pure MES micelle. Consequently, the head group repulsive interactions are much reduced, leading to an increase in aggregation number in the mixed micelles.

Table 7. Micropolarity (I_1/I_3) and binding constant (K_{SV}) for $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant system

N_{MES}	0	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9	1.0
I_1/I_3	1.22	1.20	1.19	1.17	1.16	1.11	1.10
$K_{SV} \times 10^{-4}$ ($dm^3 mol^{-1}$)	1.2	1.03	0.85	0.82	0.74	1.22	1.10

The ratio of the Ist and IIIrd vibronic peaks, I_1/I_3 in pyrene fluorescence emission spectrum is known to be sensitive to local polarity around the probe. The I_1/I_3 values obtained for this system are all greater than 1 (Table 7) suggesting a polar environment around pyrene. K_{SV} , the Stern-Volmer binding constant which is the ratio of bimolecular quenching constant to unimolecular decay constant, was also calculated using the equation²⁶,

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{SV} [Q]$$

It should also be noted that K_{SV} is equal to the product of k_q , the rate constant of quenching process and τ , the actual lifetime of fluorescence molecule in absence of bimolecular quenching. From the values of K_{SV} it can be inferred that quenching is efficient in this system and also the lifetime of pyrene is higher, if we assume that k_q s for all systems are of

Fig. 3. Plots of relative viscosity vs N_{MES} for $C_{12}E_9$ /MES system.

similar magnitude.

In Fig. 3, the relative viscosity (η_{rel}) values for 5% (w/v) $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant solutions as a function of molefraction of MES is plotted. The η_{rel} for $C_{12}E_9$ is low. Initially η_{rel} decreases at $N_{MES} = 0.1$ and then suddenly increases and shows a maximum at $N_{MES} = 0.3$. The maximum in viscosity arises due to the formation of mixed micelle. In general, η_{rel} shows positive deviation from linearity. Increase in temperature has no significant effect on the viscosity of surfactant solution.

The intrinsic viscosity $|\eta|$ was calculated using the relation,

$$|\eta| = \lim_{C \rightarrow 0} (\eta_r - 1)/C$$

where limit to zero concentration indicates that intermolecular interactions are absent. In this study we have calculated $|\eta|$ without taking the zero concentration limit. The intrinsic viscosity values (Table 8) of $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant system at all mole fractions indicate that micelles

Table 8. Intrinsic viscosity data for $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant system

N_{MES}	$ \eta , cm^3 g^{-1}$ at			
	303	308	313	318 K
0.0	8.8	8.6	8.6	8.4
0.1	5.5	5.8	5.8	5.8
0.3	9.0	9.1	8.7	9.1
0.5	8.8	8.7	8.7	8.5
0.7	8.8	8.8	9.2	9.2
0.9	9.0	8.7	9.0	9.0
1.0	6.0	6.4	6.2	6.3

are nonspherical as $|\eta|$ should be 2.5–4 $cm^3 g^{-1}$ for spherical systems²⁷ and the lowest $|\eta|$ for this system is 5.5 $cm^3 g^{-1}$. Such results on the geometry of micelles on the basis of shape factor have been reported earlier by us²⁸, and recently Soni *et al.*²⁹ also reported observations pertaining to the geometry of micelles.

Foaming : Foam heights, a measure of foamability of surfactant, were determined at 30, 35 and 40° for pure as well as mixed surfactant system and are presented in Table 9. It is clear that, foaminess in single as well as mixed surfactant system increases with increase in temperature. $C_{12}E_9$ is less foaming compared to MES and most of the molefractions of mixed system of MES. This is obvious as polyoxyethylene group in $C_{12}E_9$ has large surface area and also there is absence of surface films resulting in low foam heights¹. The foam heights in most mole fractions are higher

Table 9. Foam stability of $C_{12}E_9$ /MES mixed surfactant system as a function of temperature (average of at least two runs)

Total surfactant concentration = 5.8 mM

N_{MES}	Foam height (cms ± 0.4) at		
	30	35	40°
0.0	6.9	9.5	11.0
0.1	13.9	14.8	16.0
0.3	6.7	8.1	9.9
0.5	21.4	23.2	24.5
0.7	10.3	10.8	12.6
0.9	9.6	10.4	11.7
1.0	16.8	20.5	25.0

compared to $C_{12}E_9$, as there is possibility of rapid variation of concentration of surfactant at the air/water interface in mixed surfactant system, which is one of the main requirements of good foam forming qualities³⁰, though the higher foam height of MES compared to mixed surfactant system is difficult to explain. However, it seems that the mixed surfactant layer is a rigid one. Moreover, drainage, evaporation, interaction between environment and foams *etc.* determine the foam stability³¹.

Experimental

Nonaoxyethylene monododecyl ether [$CH_3(CH_2)_{11}(OCH_2CH_2)_9OH$], *i.e.* $C_{12}E_9$ and α -sulfonatomyristic acid methyl ester – $C_{12}H_{25}CH(SO_3Na)COOCH_3$, *i.e.* (MES) (Lion Corporation, Tokyo) were used without further purification. Cetylpyridinium chloride (Loba Chemie, India) was crystallized twice from benzene prior to use. Pyrene (Fluka, Germany) was recrystallized from cyclohexane. All solutions were prepared using double-distilled water.

Fig. 4. Representative plot of surface tension vs log concentration.

The critical micelle concentration were determined using surface tension measurements as described earlier⁵. Error in cmc values is less than $\pm 1\%$. Representative plots of

surface tension (γ) vs logarithm of surfactant concentration ($\log C$) are shown in Fig. 4.

Conductance (κ) were measured with an Equiptronics (India) conductivity bridge. A dip type cell of cell constant 1.01 cm^{-1} was used. The conductance of different solutions which were obtained on addition of aliquot of a known concentrated surfactant solution to a given volume of the

Fig. 5. Representative plot of specific conductance (κ) vs concentration of MES.

thermostated solvent were measured. Specific conductance (k) vs concentration of surfactant plots are shown in Fig. 5 for pure MES only, and no break in the specific conductance vs concentration plots was observed in any of the mixed surfactant systems.

The micellar aggregation number was determined by steady state fluorescence measurements. Pyrene was used as a probe and cetylpyridinium chloride as quencher. The excitation and emission wavelengths were 335 and 385 nm, respectively. All the fluorescence measurement was carried out at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$) using a Hitachi F-4010

Fig. 6. Representative fluorescence (emission) spectra of $10^{-6} M$ pyrene in aqueous micellar solution of $C_{12}E_9$: MES (5 : 5).

spectrophotometer. Each spectrum had one to five vibronic peaks from shorter to longer wavelengths (Fig. 6). The fluorescence intensities were monitored at 385 nm. An aliquot of the stock solution of pyrene in ethanol was transferred into a flask and the solvent was evaporated with nitrogen. The surfactant solution (10 mM) was added and concentration of pyrene was kept constant at 10^{-6} M. The quencher concentration was varied from 0 to 12×10^{-5} M. The aggregation number (N_{agg}) was deduced from the equation³²,

$$\ln I = \ln I_0 - N_{agg} [Q] / [S] - cmc$$

where [Q], [M] and [S] are the concentrations of quencher, micelle and total surfactant, respectively, I_0 and I are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher.

The ratio of intensity of first (375 nm) and third (385 nm) vibronic peaks, i.e. I_1/I_3 of the pyrene fluorescence emission spectrum in presence of surfactants is taken to be the index of micropolarity of the system, i.e. it gives an idea of microenvironment and solubilization site³³.

The viscosity of 5% (w/v) C₁₂E₉/MES mixed surfactant solution was measured using Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer at 30, 35, 40 and 45° ($\pm 1^\circ$) in a thermostated bath.

Foam height was measured using a variation of Ross-Miles method³⁴. A surfactant solution (200 ml) of known concentration (5.8 mM) was allowed a free-fall into 50 ml of the same solution through a tube (90 cm \times 1.5 cm i.d.) The reproducibility of initial foam height values was $\pm 2\%$.

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